

1 Shared human-robot proportional control of a dexterous myoelectric 2 prosthesis

3
4 Katie Z. Zhuang, Nicolas Sommer*, Vincent Mendez*, Saurav Aryan*, Emanuele Formento, Edoardo
5 D'Anna, Fiorenzo Artoni, Francesco Petrini, Giuseppe Granata, Giovanni Cannaviello, Wassim
6 Raffoul, Aude Billard#, and Silvestro Micera#

7
8 (* Equal contribution as junior authors, # Equal contribution as senior authors)

9
10 **Myoelectric prostheses allow users to recover lost functionality by controlling a robotic device with their**
11 **remaining muscle activity. Such commercial devices can give users a high level of autonomy, but still do not**
12 **approach the dexterity of the intact human hand. We present here a method to control a robotic hand,**
13 **shared between user intention and robotic automation. The algorithm allows user-controlled movements**
14 **when high dexterity is desired, but also assisted grasping when robustness is paramount. This combination**
15 **of features is currently lacking in commercial prostheses and can greatly improve prosthesis usability. First,**
16 **we design and test a myoelectric proportional controller that can predict multiple joint angles**
17 **simultaneously and with high accuracy. We then implement online control with both able-bodied and**
18 **amputee subjects. Finally, we present a shared control scheme in which robotic automation aids in object**
19 **grasping by maximizing contact area between hand and object, greatly increasing grasp success and object**
20 **hold times in both a virtual and a physical environment. Our results present a viable method of prosthesis**
21 **control implemented in real time, for reliable articulation of multiple simultaneous degrees of freedom.**

22
23 In the United States alone, about 1.6 million people live with an amputation, 541,000 of which
24 affect the upper limbs¹. This condition diminishes quality of life, mobility and independence, while also
25 imparting a social stigma². Upper limb prostheses controlled using surface electromyographic (sEMG)
26 signals attempt to restore hand and arm functionality by using the amputee's remaining muscle activity
27 to control movements of a prosthetic device. However, the capabilities of current commercial
28 prostheses are still grossly inferior compared to the dexterity of the human hand. Commercial devices
29 usually use a two-recording-channel system to control a single degree of freedom (DoF), i.e. one
30 sEMG channel for flexion and one for extension³. While intuitive, the system provides little dexterity.
31 Patients abandon myoelectric prostheses at high rates, in part because they feel that the level of
32 control is insufficient to merit the price and complexity of these devices⁴⁻⁶. In recent years, various
33 research groups have made significant advances in myoelectric prosthesis control in laboratory and
34 prototype environments. Many groups have demonstrated great success in grasp classification, which
35 is a common approach for prosthesis control, but limits the user to a library of trained hand postures⁷⁻
36 ¹⁰. However a few groups have now attempted to decode single finger movements¹¹⁻¹³. Despite high
37 decoding accuracy, these studies showed results mainly from able-bodied subjects performing offline
38 tests. With cited decoding performances of upwards of 90-95% for each method, we see a clear
39 dichotomy between laboratory experiments and clinical viability, a point that is addressed by Jiang et
40 al¹⁴.

41 The idea of "shared control", that is, automation of some portion of the motor command, is already a
42 topic of interest within the field of robotics and neuroengineering¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Indeed, shared control
43 approach can play a key role in robotic applications involving human-robot interfacing such as
44 prosthetic body parts. The limited sensory-motor control abilities in this case make the subjects

45 unable to conform their fingers to the shape of the object. This in turn inhibits their ability to secure
46 and adapt their grasp according to the requirement of the task. Shared control can fill this void by
47 stabilizing the grasp, making fine adjustments to the fingers by processing information from the tactile
48 sensors placed on prosthetic hand's fingers. More generally speaking, shared control strategies aim
49 to bridge the gap between human's intentions and efficient execution of the intended task by using
50 information from the sensors.

51 Even if potentially useful, shared control has not yet become prevalent in the area of peripheral nerve
52 interfaces. Došen et al. propose a camera-based approach¹⁹ while Light et al. proposes 1-DoF control
53 with automated grip force adjustment²⁰. Other methods of automation include automated hand-closing
54 in response to slippage²¹ and underactuated systems in which spring-like mechanisms mediate grasp
55 force²². The only commercial application of shared-control methods to date is the Ottobock
56 Sensorhand Speed which automatically increases thumb flexion during grasping in response to
57 slippage¹⁸. However, it is only capable of binary action choices or 1-DoF proportional velocity control.

58 The control method presented here attempts to implement a shared-control strategy with a
59 highly-dexterous hand prosthesis by taking advantage of state-of-the art myoelectric decoding as well
60 as an algorithmic controller for grasp optimization. We first propose a kinematic proportional decoder
61 using a multilayer perceptron (MLP), which allows users to simultaneously and continuously control
62 each finger individually. In addition, we propose to integrate and use a shared-control scheme in
63 which a robotic controller aids in stable grasping by maximizing the area of contact between a
64 prosthetic hand and an object²³. The idea behind this scheme is to make object grasping more robust
65 (avoiding accidental drops) while allowing the user to maintain full autonomy over grasping or
66 releasing, grasp preshaping, and non-grasp-related motions. In this way, we achieve both highly
67 dexterous user control when precise positioning is valuable, and partially automated grasp attainment
68 when object droppage avoidance desirable.

69

70 **Results**

71 We performed three sets of experiments in which we decoded hand movements of subjects using
72 sEMG signals recorded from their forearms. We recruited three subjects with hand/transradial
73 amputations (subjects A1, A2 and A3) and eight able-bodied subjects (subjects B1, B2, B3, B4, S1,
74 S2, S3, S4) for the study. In the first set of experiments, able and amputee subjects performed online
75 control of a virtual prosthetic hand. In the second set of experiments, the same subjects used a virtual
76 hand to grasp and release virtual objects according to visual cues in two conditions: with or without
77 robotic assistance. In the third set of experiments, four able-bodied subjects controlled a physical
78 robotic arm and hand to perform functional object manipulation tasks.

79
 80 **Figure 1.** Experimental Setup and Subjects. **a**, In online experiments, four able-bodied subjects and three amputee subjects controlled a
 81 virtual robotic hand using their surface EMG signals. The signals were decoded with a multilayer perceptron to obtain predictions of single-
 82 digit joint angles. **b**, The three amputee subjects had varying levels of amputation, shown here. **c**, Movements we tested consisted of both
 83 single-digit and multi-digit movements. All subjects performed all movements except Subject A2 who did not perform index and middle
 84 finger flexion/extensions independently.

85
 86 **Experiment 1 (Online Kinematic Decoding).** Three amputee subjects (A1, A2 and A3 in Figure 1b) and four able subjects (B1, B2, B3, and B4)
 87 performed online control of a virtual prosthetic hand with sEMG decoding. To train the MLP, subjects were asked to mimic the movements of the virtual hand
 88 while sEMGs were recorded. We decoded flexion and extension of each digit as well as thumb opposition and reposition. This gave DoFs per subject for all subjects except subject A2 who moved
 89 the index and middle fingers concurrently (Figure 1c). The average per-session correlation for all subjects and all sessions was 0.52 and the peak-to-peak normalized mean square error²⁴ (nMSE)
 90 was 15.7%. For all subjects, the MLP successfully predicts the flexion and extension of each finger, both individually and simultaneously with flexion of other digits. We summarize performance in
 91 Supplementary Table 1 for all subjects and sessions.

92
 93 In order to further analyze the ability of the decoder to predict the desired joint angles and to compare these predictions against chance, we computed the percentage of time of correctly predicted
 94 joint angles for each subject (Figure 2a). As a control for this assessment, we selected random angles
 95
 96
 97
 98

99 from the training set range and computed prediction accuracy using the random angle as the
100 instructed one (white sections). This way, we were able to simulate chance accuracy of the MLP
101 predictions. We find that in every degree of freedom for Subject A3, the MLP is able to decode
102 significantly higher than chance (Wilcoxon two-sided signed rank test, $p < 0.01$). The same analysis
103 was performed for all subjects individually with similar results (Supplementary Figure 2) using a non-
104 parametric test due to non-normal data (Kornogorov-Smirnoff test). We then performed this analysis
105 for all subjects while pooling all of the degrees of freedom to obtain an overall measure of decoding
106 performance (Figure 2b).

107 To analyze any patterns in prediction error, we calculated a “confusion matrix” for each degree
108 of freedom (Figure 2c). Here, we enforced a threshold (mean prediction angle) to separate joint
109 predictions into either flexion or extension. We also mapped the instructed joint angles into flexion or
110 extension using mean instructed angle for thresholding. Plotting instructed activation on the x-axis
111 and performed action on the y-axis, we color map excessive action (false positive) to orange intensity
112 and lack of action (false negative) to blue intensity. We observed that Subject A3 has trouble
113 controlling thumb flexion; it is excessively flexed during the actions of other fingers. Similarly, Subject
114 A2, who has extensive median nerve damage, has difficulty controlling the thumb, index and middle
115 fingers movements.

116 These thresholded decoding accuracies are within a similar range as the ones obtained in
117 online classification of finger flexion and extension cited by Cipriani et al. (79% average accuracy for
118 amputees cited vs. our average of 89.5% for a similar number of classes: 7 classes cited vs. our 6
119 effective classes which are simultaneously considered).¹²

120

121

122

123

124

125

126

127

128

129

130

131

132

133

134

135

136

137

138

139

140

141

Figure 2. Analysis of online prediction performance of the MLP. **a**, Prediction accuracy of the MLP compared to chance accuracy. Gray boxplots indicate the fraction of time per trial that each predicted DoF is within 15 degrees of the instructed angle. White boxplots indicate the fraction of time per trial that a random angle (within the set of trained angles) is within 15 degrees of the instructed angle. Each degree of freedom was predicted higher than chance level ($p < 0.01$ Wilcoxon two-sided signed rank test). All box plots in this manuscript include a median center line (red), box edges at 25th and 75th percentiles, notches calculated based on interquartile range $\pm \frac{1.57 \cdot IQR}{\sqrt{n}}$. **b**, Overall decoding accuracy versus chance for all subjects. Statistical significance is calculated with the Wilcoxon two-sided signed rank test. **c**, Confusion matrix of each digit's degrees of freedom for one subject. Blue pixels indicate lack of specified movement when instructed (false negatives) while more orange pixels indicate undesired movements (false positives). Overall error is calculated as well as error along the diagonal of the matrix (whether the instructed motion was performed accurately). **d**, Confusion matrices for three other subjects.

This experiment demonstrates our ability to decode individual finger movements proportionally for multiple simultaneous DoFs and in real time using noninvasive sEMG signals. Performance results are not only above chance level, but robust for all tested movements for both able-bodied subjects as well as amputee subjects.

Experiment 2 (Shared Control using the virtual environment). In this set of experiments, the user attempted to grasp, hold and then release virtual objects by controlling a sensorized virtual robotic hand implemented in Gazebo and rviz, a ROS package (Figure 3a). The same subjects from Experiment 1 performed this experiment with the exception of subject B1. In addition to the MLP decoding, we tested two conditions: one *with* shared control for partial grasp automation (shared control) and one *without* (MLP only). During the shared control condition, the virtual hand would

142 automatically attempt to maximize contact between the hand and a grasped object by increasing
143 flexion of a finger as soon as a single phalanx touches an object. If, however, the total joint angle
144 difference between MLP predictions and shared control targets of a single digit would differ by more
145 than 50 degrees, the controller would use torque control to achieve MLP-decoded joint angles for that
146 digit (Figure 3b). This threshold was chosen empirically from preliminary testing. In the future, we will
147 strive to make the transition gradual instead using a threshold. The action of the algorithm is shown
148 in Figure 3c under the conditions of pre-contact (MLP joint targets), initial contact (shared control
149 targets in red) and achievement of full contact (in green). Figure 4d shows an example of single-digit
150 flexion and extension with or without shared control for Subject B4 grasping the thin rectangular bar.
151 We see that when shared control is implemented, digits that make initial contact with an object are
152 better able to achieve more contacts and maintain them. The higher number of contacts achieved
153 with shared control reflects this advantage (top row). However, the user is still able to release the
154 object when it is desired (movement instructions at bottom).

155 In Figures 3e, 4a we show the percentage of trials in which a full grasp is achieved per subject across
156 all sessions with either shared control or only MLP predictions. Full grasp is defined as attaining all
157 possible contacts between the hand and a particular object (see Methods). In the shared control
158 condition, subjects are able to achieve considerably more successful grasp trials for all objects. For

159 each object and for each subject, we also show percentage change in fraction of successful grasp
 160 trials between the MLP-only and shared control conditions (Figure 4b).

161
 162 **Figure 3.** Shared control in virtual environment, setup and results. **a**, Simulator of Allegro Hand **b**, Shared control scheme. Both the MLP
 163 decoder and shared controller run simultaneously and the MLP-decoded joint targets prevail before contact. During object contact, the
 164 shared control joint targets prevail unless the difference between MLP-only and shared control is above a 50-degree threshold. **c**, Action of
 165 the active compliant contact controller. When one contact on a digit touches the object, the direction of motion is computed to bring other
 166 contacts of the digit towards the object. Figure adapted from Sommer and Billard et al.²³ **d**, Example traces of shared control (Subject B4).
 167 Top row shows total of pressure detected without (left) and with (right) shared control. Traces show the joint angle for each DoF. Dotted
 168 lines indicate the MLP prediction while solid traces indicate the actual position of the virtual robotic hand. Bottom row indicates the cues to
 169 grasp or release. **e**, Percentage of trials during which desired contacts are achieved for the three objects by Subject B5 over 3 sessions.
 170 (p-values from Fisher's two-tailed exact test). Number of successful trials versus total trials are indicated on each bar. **f**, Duration of hold
 171 time for each object out of seven seconds (p-values from Wilcoxon two-sided signed-rank test). **g**, Percentage of grasping trial time during
 172 which contacts were touching the objects (p-values from Fisher's two-tailed exact test). Contacts on different phalanges are indicated with
 173 different color shades, raw numbers for calculation included in Supplementary Table 1.

174 We also see a difference in grasping performance between objects grasped which is subject-
175 dependent. For example, Subject A2 benefitted the most from shared control for the rectangular bar.
176 This result is consistent with the finding that the same subject has particular difficulty in sustaining
177 muscle activation associated with the thumb, index and middle fingers due to median nerve damage.

178 In addition to the attainment of grasp, we also assessed how long the subjects were able to
179 maintain holds. Figure 3f, 4c shows the distribution of hold times per object and per subject with or
180 without shared control. We define hold time as the length of continuous time during which the subject
181 could maintain required contacts between the virtual hand and object without any contacts being
182 broken²⁵. Due to the visual cue, a small percentage of non-hold time is likely due to subject reaction
183 time. For all objects and subjects, hold times are greater with the shared control condition than only
184 MLP, with the exception of the cylinder for subject B2. This may be due to the low number of trials
185 subject B2 performed in comparison to Subjects A1-3. .

186 Finally, we assess the percentage of time that each single sensor contacted the objects to
187 analyze which contacts subjects found more difficult to maintain. For all objects, all subjects were able
188 to maintain longer contacts with all parts of the digits with shared control than with only MLP
189 predictions. Importantly, all subjects were capable of releasing the objects once grasped by relaxing
190 their grasp (Fig. 4d, 6b).

191 Taken together, these results show that the shared controller aids grasping in multiple ways,
192 namely facilitating longer, more successful grasps and avoiding accidental drops.

193
 194 **Figure 4.** Shared Control results in virtual environment cont'd. **a**, Comparison of fraction of successful grasping trials with (orange) or
 195 without (black) shared controller aid for three amputee subjects and all three object types. Data are shown for all sessions of each subject
 196 (# of sessions indicated in title). Statistical p-values are computed using Fisher's two-tailed exact test. Number of successful trials versus
 197 total trials are indicated on each bar. **b**, Percentage improvement in fraction of correct trials for the three subjects split by object type. Each
 198 color indicates a different subject. **c**, Duration of hold time for each object with or without shared control for the three subjects (p-values by
 199 Wilcoxon two-sided signed-rank test). Maximum instructed hold time was seven seconds. **d**, Percentage of grasping trial time during which
 200 each single contact on each digit made contact with the objects with or without shared control for the three subjects (p-values by Fisher's
 201 two-tailed Exact Test). Each plot is for a different subject with the shaded bars indicating contact placement. Lighter color shades indicate
 202 more proximal phalanges on the same digit. Data are aggregated over all trials and sessions for a single subject, raw numbers for calculation
 203 included in Supplementary Table 2.

204 **Experiment 3 (Shared Control in a physical environment).**

205 This experiment was divided into two sub-experiments. In the first sub-experiment, the subjects
 206 performed a variant of the box and block test²⁶ through teleoperation of a physical robotic hand and
 207 arm. The goal was to grasp and move an object (a bottle, half-filled of water) placed on a hard case
 208 to another one placed approximately 30cm away. Object droppage was considered a failed trial. The
 209 subjects controlled the robotic arm via an optical motion capture system. A robotic hand (the physical
 210 analog of the virtual one described in Experiment 2) was mounted onto the robotic arm and controlled
 211 with either MLP only or shared control. Four able-bodied subjects participated in this experiment (S1,
 212 S2, S3 and S4). After a training phase to train the MLP decoders, the subjects were required to

213 perform 20 trials of the functional task under in each condition (randomized MLP only and shared
 214 control) for a total of 40 trials.
 215

216 **Figure 5. Shared control in physical environment, setup and results.** **a**, Comparison of MLP fraction of successful trials for the box and
 217 blocks task and the manipulation task with shared control (orange) and without (black). Data are shown for all sessions of each subject.
 218 Number of successful trials versus total trials are indicated on each bar when not zero. For the manipulation task (right panel), the total
 219 number of successful trials in each condition was summed over all the subjects. Fisher’s two-tailed exact test was used to compute statistical
 220 p-values for individual subjects, Wilcoxon rank-sum test was used for total values. **b**, Effective normalized pressure on each finger
 221 comparing the trials with and without shared control. The p-values indicated were computed using Wilcoxon’s rank-sum test. **c**, Number of
 222 contacts detected by pressure sensors on each finger, averaged over time of each trial. The bars indicate the mean of each trial’s average
 223 number of contacts. The p-value is computed using Wilcoxon’s rank-sum test to compare trials of all subjects with and without shared

224 control. **d**, Time series plots of total pressure, MLP decoded joint positions (dotted) and corresponding actual joint positions of the allegro
225 hand (solid) over few sample grasping trials. The joints on each finger were summed over phalanges. Total pressure was computed by
226 summing over all phalanges after normalization. **e**, Picture of the setup comprising the robotic arm and hand with a subject wearing the
227 EMG acquisition system. **f**, Snapshots of completion of box and blocks task (top) and manipulation task (bottom). For full video see
228 supplementary video 3. One trial of each condition (with and without shared-control) can be seen in supplementary video 4.

229 Results are shown in Figure 5a (left panel). S3 and S4 performed significantly better with
230 shared control than without whereas S1 and S2 were highly successful at the task in both conditions.

231 To evaluate whether the shared control improves grasp quality, we defined two metrics based
232 on the pressure sensor data: average number of contacts and the “effective normalized pressure”
233 (see Methods). The results shown in figures 5b and 5c indicate better performance with shared control
234 in terms of both of the two metrics. The p-values, computed using Wilcoxon’s rank-sum test over all
235 trials by all subjects, show statistical significance in case of effective normal pressure ($p < 0.0001$).
236 The same test performed on average number of contacts was not significant for the index finger
237 ($p=0.07$) but showed statistical significance for the other two fingers ($p < 0.05$).

238 As shared control was notably advantageous for the subject S3, we compared the timeseries
239 plots of a few trials from the subject’s box and block tasks (Figure 5d). In open position (close to zero),
240 the actual position (solid line) closely follows the MLP prediction (dotted line) for each finger. However,
241 the subject cannot close the fingers enough to grasp, leading to insufficient total pressure. With the
242 shared control, the grasps are tightened to achieve the desired pressure. In case of the subjects who
243 performed equally well with and without shared control (S1, S2) the MLP prediction by itself was high
244 enough during grasping to achieve a tight grip and high pressure.

245 The second sub-experiment used the same training protocol as first, with a slight variation in
246 the behavioral task. The task here consisted of grasping the bottle from the table, bringing it to mouth,
247 tilting it to mimic drinking and then returning the bottle back to a steady position (a few centimeters
248 above the table). Subjects were given less than 10 seconds to complete the movement and then hold
249 the bottle in steady position for at least 10 seconds. The rotation of partially filled bottle leads to the
250 shifting of its moment of inertia due to flow of the water, resulting in a perturbation. Additionally, bottle’s
251 conical shape and smooth surface further adds to sliding of the bottle. Thus, this sub-task can
252 evaluate the potential of shared control in stabilizing the grasp under object’s perturbations, slippery
253 surface and non-uniform shape of object. S1, S2 and S3 performed better with shared control but not
254 significantly (S1 and S3: $p=0.3$, S2: $p=0.65$) while S4 showed statistically significant improvement
255 (Figure 5a right). This is likely due to the limited number of trials. Moreover, S4 was completely
256 unsuccessful at completing the task without shared control but performed relatively well with shared
257 control ($p < 0.01$). The overall advantage of using the shared control becomes evident when we pool
258 together all the subjects (see last histograms in Figure 5b).

259

260 Discussion

261 Here we show that we are able to decode single finger kinematics from surface EMGs of both able
262 and amputee subjects. The decoding approach was accurate for both single-finger movements and
263 coordinated, simultaneously activated grasping motions. We also show that decoding is fast enough
264 for real-time applications, with an update rate of 33 Hz. To the best of our knowledge, the work
265 presented here is the first demonstration of a real-time proportional decoder for individual fingers
266 tested with amputee subjects.

267 One reason commercial prostheses prefer to implement classifier-based decoders instead of
268 proportional ones is the robustness of classifiers in remaining in a particular posture. For grasping,
269 this type of control is ideal to prevent accidental dropping but sacrifices user agency by restricting the
270 number of possible hand postures. Our implementation of shared control allows for both user agency

271 and grasping robustness. In free space, the user has full control over hand movements, which also
272 allows for volitional pre-shaping for grasping.

273 The tests performed in a physical environment allowed us to show the efficacy of shared
274 control to the improvement of grasp especially when complex tasks are implemented (see Figure 5b).
275 For the first simpler sub-experiment, some subjects (S1 and S2) performed the tasks equally well
276 regardless of the use of shared control while others (S3 and S4) benefitted from shared control
277 significantly. This was because the MLP prediction performance varies across the subjects. These
278 results show that the use of the shared control can be particularly useful for subjects with limited EMG
279 control ability.

280 Another advantage of shared control is that it requires less energy for the user to maintain a
281 grasp¹⁴. Muscle fatigue is well-documented in sEMG studies²⁷⁻³¹ and is one hurdle for proportionally
282 controlled prostheses. Without the presence of sensory feedback, the simplest solution for a user to
283 be sure of sufficient force is to flex the fingers maximally throughout the duration of the grasp, which
284 can be very fatiguing. In Figure 6b and 6c we show EMG activity of Subject B2 during grasping with
285 shared control or with only MLP predictions. Figure 6b shows averaged EMG activity across all
286 channels and all grasp trials of each object type in a session. As can be seen, for all objects, EMG
287 amplitude is lower with shared control ($p < 0.01$ Wilcoxon two-sided signed rank test). As a control, we
288 also plot averaged EMG during release trials (Fig. 6b right) which reveals low EMG activity for all
289 objects, after a short peak at the beginning of the trial during which the subject reacts to the visual
290 cue to release. Figure 6c shows the averaged EMG for each individual channel and for each individual
291 object averaged across trials with only MLP predictions (left) or shared control (right). We observe a
292 clear difference in overall muscle activation. This effect on EMG activity was also confirmed during
293 Experiment 3. Figure 6d shows averaged EMG activity across all grasps and all EMG channels for
294 each subject. EMG activity is significantly different for subject S1 and S4 ($p < 0.01$, Wilcoxon two-sided
295 signed rank test), but not for S2 ($p = 0.64$) and S3 ($p = 0.61$). It is interesting to note that even two
296 subjects performed well for the box and blocks test in both conditions (see Fig. 5a), the overall muscle
297 activation is clearly lower during shared control than the MLP-only condition. We find the same result
298 when we analyze each EMG channel separately (Figure 6e).

299 In our study, inter-subject decoding performance was highly inconsistent. For amputee
300 subjects, many factors can contribute to this heterogeneity, including the level of amputation (Figure
301 1b), type of injury and time since injury. In Figure 6a we plot the correlation coefficient between the
302 EMG channels we recorded from for each subject. We see that subjects A1 and A3 have relatively
303 uncorrelated EMG channels whereas subject A2 has highly correlated channels. This indicates
304 inability to activate different muscle groups independently. Functionally, this results in subject A2's
305 inability to perform all of the single-digit movements that the other subjects were able to. In addition to
306 a lower number of DoFs independently required for subject A2 (index and middle fingers moved
307 together), we show that shared control can be particularly effective for subjects with few independent
308 muscle groups. We emphasize this point because regardless of the type of decoding algorithm one
309 would implement, the subjects with lower neuromuscular ability will suffer lower decoding accuracy
310 unless they can use some kind of compensation. Such compensation can be surgical, such as in

311 targeted muscle innervation, behavioral, such as learning to contract in an unintuitive way, or it could
 312 be algorithmic, as we implemented.

313
 314
 315 **Figure 6.** EMG analysis with and without shared control. **a**, Cross-correlation of EMG activity between each of the recorded channels for
 316 four subjects during a single session of MLP decoding. Darker pixels indicate lower correlation between pairs of EMG channels while
 317 brighter pixels indicate high correlation. High correlation is a proxy for muscle coactivation. **b**, Averaged sEMG amplitude during grasping
 318 trials for Subject B2 for the three objects in the virtual environment. Solid lines indicate EMG amplitude during grasp trials of shared control
 319 and dashed lines indicate average EMG amplitudes during trials with only MLP control (left). The same plot is shown for release trials: when
 320 the subject was instructed to release the object (right). **c**, Per-channel EMG activity during grasp trials of each object for Subject B2. Each
 321 row is normalized amplitude of a single EMG channel averaged over all grasping trials for a particular object. **d**, Averaged EMG activity
 322 during grasps of the physical box and block task for each subject. Activity is averaged across all grasps and all channels per subject. **e**,
 323 Per-channel EMG activity of grasps during one session of the physical box and blocks task for each Subject. Each row is normalized
 324 amplitude of a single EMG channel averaged over all trials for a particular subject.

325
 326 As of now, the compliance controller implemented in our shared control has only one set target
 327 force for applying pressure on grasped objects. Future studies should include user-modulated forces,
 328 which would be greatly aided with the addition of sensory feedback.

329 In conclusion, we have explored sEMG-control of individual finger movements in real time with
 330 both able-bodied and amputee subjects and show the advantages of a shared-control scheme. In
 331 particular, our shared controller leverages the dexterity afforded by user control with the grasp
 332 robustness of automation, which can greatly benefit the translation of myoelectric control algorithms
 333 into commercial devices. Furthermore, we recognize that amputees and even able users are
 334 extremely varied in their ability to modulate their remaining muscle activity. Consequently, some

335 subjects will be less able to control as many DoFs, or as consistently, as others. Shared control can
336 particularly help these users who are less proficient in sEMG modulation and additionally may prevent
337 premature fatigue. Thus, control algorithms should account for user variance and partial automation
338 is one such method that can greatly improve myoelectric prosthesis usability. In the next future, we
339 believe that this approach could be valuable to cope also for the limitation of other human-robot
340 interfaces such as the ones based on brain signals or body movements.

341

342 **Methods**

343 **Subjects and EMG recording.** Three amputee subjects were recruited for this study, two female
344 (Subjects A2 and A3) aged 53 and 49, respectively, and one male (Subject A1) 69 years of age.
345 Subjects A1 and A2 had proximal transradial amputations while subject A3 had a right hand
346 amputation just distal to the wrist (Figure 1). In addition, seven able bodied subjects were recruited,
347 all of whom were male, between 26 and 30 years of age for experiment 1 and 2. Subject B6 was left-
348 handed and performed all experiments with the left hand. Four additional male subjects aged between
349 20 and 26 (S1, S2, S3, and S4) were recruited for the third experiment with the physical robot. Ethical
350 approval was obtained by the Institutional Ethics Committees of Policlinic A. Gemelli at the Catholic
351 University, the Italian Ministry of Health, and the cantonal ethical committee of Vaud. Informed
352 consent was obtained from all participants in the study.

353 In Experiments 1 and 2, we collected data from three able-bodied subjects (subjects B2, B3,
354 and B4) and all three amputee subjects. Subject B1 performed only Experiment 1. For the three
355 experiments, we used the Noraxon Delsys system connected to a LabJack data acquisition card to
356 wirelessly record from five to seven bipolar surface EMG channels at 2kHz from each subject. In
357 general, we tried to use the fewest possible channels that could result in full DoF control in order to
358 show translational potential. Thus, we opted for five channels for subjects A2, B1, B2, B3, B4 and
359 seven channels from A1 and A3 and finally six for S1, S2 and S3. We started with using five EMG
360 channels per subject. For the amputee subjects, we attempted to add more electrodes to improve
361 decoding performance. Subject A2, however, had very limited surface area on the remaining forearm
362 and so we were unable to use any additional electrodes. For the able subjects, the muscles targeted
363 were the extensor digitorum, flexor carpi radialis, palmaris longus, flexor digitorum superficialis and
364 flexor carpi ulnaris, located with palpation. Due to the differences in the cause of amputation (ex.
365 Torsion vs. lacerating), remaining muscles in the forearm differed in placement from non-amputees
366 so palpation of the stump for controllable muscle tone determined electrode placement.

367

368 **EMG processing and Feature Extraction.** We chose eight well-explored time-domain features to
369 extract for both experiments 1 and 2^{32,33}:

- 370
- 371 • Mean absolute value
 - 372 • Zero crossing: number of time that the amplitude value of the EMG crosses zero
 - 373 • Slope sign changes: number of times that the slope of the EMG amplitude changes sign
 - 374 • Waveform length: cumulative length of the EMG waveform
 - 375 • Log detector: $e^{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log(|x_i|)}$ where x_i is the EMG amplitude at time bin i .
 - 376 • Root mean square of EMG amplitude
 - 377 • Willison amplitude: number of times the difference between two EMG neighboring samples is
378 greater than a certain threshold. In the implemented code, the threshold has been set to 0.2
379 times the value of the standard deviation of the global signal.
 - Maximum absolute value was used only in Experiment 3.

380 In Experiment 1, all seven features of all channels became the inputs of the multilayer perceptron
381 model. In experiments 1 and 2, we used a 100ms-sliding window with 50ms of overlap to calculate
382 features, downsampled to 30Hz for the online experiments.

383 For a preliminary offline experiment (Supplementary Figure 1), we also calculated four autoregressive
384 features. Before fitting the MLP, we performed both channel and feature selection so not all features
385 were included in the network training. In channel selection, one MLP was first trained and tested for
386 each EMG channel. The channel providing the highest estimation performance was chosen as the
387 first optimal channel. In the second fit iteration, the previously selected channel was paired with each
388 of the remaining channels. These pairs were then used to train and test other MLPs. Again, the pair
389 providing the highest estimation performance was chosen as the optimal subset of two channels. This
390 procedure was repeated until either the increase in coefficient of determination (R^2) after adding one
391 channel was less than 0.01 or a limit of 5 channels was reached. For feature selection, the same
392 forward selection algorithm as for channel selection was used, repeating as long as the increase in
393 R^2 after adding one feature was greater than 0.01. For the third experiments, we used a 300ms sliding
394 window with 30ms overlap to extract features offline. Online frequency was kept the same, no feature
395 selection was applied nor channel selection.

396 397 **Experiments in a virtual environment (Experiments 1 and 2)**

398 Experiment 1 began with a training period lasting approximately 3 minutes. The subject
399 watched a series of movements on a screen performed by a pair of virtual robotic hands (Modular
400 Prosthetic Limb by Johns Hopkins University Advanced Physics laboratory). The subject was
401 instructed to try to copy the movements on the screen with mirrored movement (imagined movement
402 of the phantom hand in the case of amputees). Each movement was repeated three times, each with
403 a hold period of approximately five seconds. sEMG activity from the stump of the amputation
404 (decomposed into features) and the directed movements of the virtual hand served as training signals
405 for the MLP. Thus, we assumed perfect tracking between the subject and the movements presented
406 on the screen. We asked subjects to perform single finger flexions and extensions, thumb opposition,
407 closed hand, three-finger pinch, ulnar grasp, and open hand (Figure 1c). Due to subject A2's lack of
408 residual active muscle, we asked only this subject to perform thumb opposition, index and middle
409 finger combined flexions and extensions, closed hand, three-finger pinch, ulnar grasp and open hand.
410 After the training period, subjects attempted to repeat these movements in random order, using the
411 MLP prediction output. Again, they were cued with the virtual hand movements. Each movement was
412 repeated five times. Either the right or left hand of the virtual hand performed the desired movement,
413 which the subjects attempted to follow, while the other virtual hand showed the MLP-decoded output.
414 The controllable virtual hand was ipsilateral to the amputation for amputee subjects and the dominant
415 hand for able subjects.

416 During shared control, Experiment 2, the MLP output controlled one virtual hand for grasping
417 objects. Subjects used a color cue (red/green) to signal when to grasp and release each object. Each
418 grasp or release phase lasted seven seconds. The virtual objects presented were a cylinder, a cross-
419 shaped joint, and a thin rectangular bar in one of three different orientations per object (rotations
420 around either the x, y or z axes) presented at random. Subjects controlled the hand with MLP
421 predictions of four digits: thumb, index, middle and either the ring or the pinky finger for the last finger
422 of the Allegro Hand simulation. From the virtual environment, we are able to record data from the
423 hand's contact sensors and hence are able to assess hand-to-object contact as well as hold time. For
424 each object, we defined required contacts for a successful trial based on the contacts that were
425 physically attainable. For the cylinder, required contacts were proximal interphalangeal and
426 metacarpophalangeal contacts on every digit, for the cross-joint, required contacts were distal and
427 proximal interphalangeal contacts on every digit, and for the rectangular bar, required contacts were

428 the distal phalanges of the index and ring fingers and the thumb. A trial was a success if the subject
429 was able to achieve all required contacts simultaneously.

430

431 **Experimental Hardware description**

432 The hardware for the final “physical” experiments consists of an Allegro hand mounted on the KUKA
433 IIWA 7 robot, OptiTrack camera system and TEKSCAN pressure sensors. The *right* allegro hand
434 consists of three fingers and a thumb, each with four degrees of freedom. The fingers have four
435 motors, one each at the MCP, PIP and DIP joints while the fourth motor is located just under the finger
436 base, where it is attached to the palm and controls its lateral rotation. The thumb has three motors
437 located at the joint connecting to the palm, controlling rotations along the three axes and one motor
438 located at the joint connecting the two phalanges. Each of the 16 motors can be operated in position
439 control or torque control mode, the later being used in shared control approach. A set of two
440 TEKSCAN tactile sensor GRIP system is mounted on the allegro hand to obtain contact and pressure
441 information at the phalanges. Due to an issue with the third finger, we had to restrain its motion
442 completely and work with the thumb and other two fingers in all our experiments.

443 The allegro hand is mounted on KUKA arm so that it can be moved around in space by the subject.
444 The subject wears a set of three OptiTrack markers on the wrist, using which the position and
445 orientation of the subject’s hand can be detected by a set of 7 infrared camera. The EE of KUKA is
446 then sent the same to move it in tandem with subject’s hand. KUKA IIWA 7 robot has 7 degrees of
447 freedom, which allows its end-effector (EE) to be moved in desired position and orientation in smooth
448 and continuous manner. An inverse-kinematics solver decodes the EE position and orientation into
449 the individual desired joint positions, and sends them to the KUKA arm’s controller.

450

451

452 **Protocols of the “physical” experiments (Experiment 3).**

453 These experiments began with a training period lasting 4 and a half minutes. The subject watched a
454 series of movements on a screen performed by the same virtual environment as experiments 1 and
455 2. Each movement was repeated five times, each with a hold period of approximately five seconds.
456 sEMG activity from the forearm of the subjects (decomposed into features) and the directed
457 movements of the virtual hand served as training signals for the MLP. Thus, we assumed perfect
458 tracking between the subject and the movements presented on the screen. At the end of this task,
459 the MLP was trained.

460 For the “box and block” task, two hard cases were placed on a table in front of the robot with
461 a bottle of water placed on one of them. Subjects were instructed to grab a bottle of water (Badoit 1L)
462 and move it from one box to the other. They could grasp it freely and change grip position until they
463 felt confident enough to lift it up. A trial was considered as success if the bottle was moved from one
464 box to the other without droppage before reaching the second box. If the subject knocked over the
465 bottle while trying to grasp it, the experimenter put it back at initial condition and the trial was not
466 considered as fail.

467 During these experiments, several metrics were used to assess the performance of the
468 subjects:

- 469 1. Number of successful trials performed by the subject. A trial was considered as failure if the bottle
470 fell in the gap between the two boxes.
- 471 2. Time to perform the overall task
- 472 3. Average number of contacts and the “effective normalized pressure”. These two parameters were
473 used to characterize the quality of grasping. Owing to the varying sensitivity of the sensors,
474 pressure of each sensor data was first normalized by dividing by the maximum detected value of
475 the respective sensors. The normalized data were used in rest of the evaluations. The average

476 number of contacts on each finger was computed by summing the number of contacts detected
477 on each finger and averaged over the grasping time of each trial. Whereas, the effective normal
478 pressure is defined as the sum of maximum normalized pressure detected on all phalanges of a
479 finger weighed by the average contact time of the respective phalange during the grasping period
480 of a given trial. Usually, a greater number of contacts on each finger tends to make the grasp
481 more stable against perturbation. Further, higher pressure and duration of contact are expected
482 to improve the grasp in a task such as block test. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the
483 two metrics defined here can be used to test shared control's performance in improving the grasp.
484

485 For the manipulation task, the same bottle was placed on a table in front of the robot. Subjects
486 were instructed to grasp and lift the bottle, then tilt their arm as if they were drinking from it. The trial
487 was considered successful if the water flowed to the other side of the bottle (touching the bottle cap).
488 The subject was then required to return the arm to initial position, and then hold the bottle in the air
489 above the table for 10 seconds without any slippage. The experimenter verified that the bottle-tilt
490 movement phase was completed within ten seconds and that the post-movement hold period also
491 lasted 10 seconds. The MLP was retrained between the two behavioral sessions to avoid any loss of
492 performance and the order between the two conditions (MLP only and shared control) was reversed
493 for each subject compared to the first session.
494

495 **Multilayer perceptron model.** We chose to use the multilayer perceptron as the decoding method
496 for decoding finger kinematics due to its extensive use in sEMG applications³⁴. For experiment 1 and
497 2, we chose a three-layer network with one input layer, one hidden layer with three neurons and an
498 output layer. The input layer is composed of the different features extracted from sEMG data and the
499 number of nodes is dependent on the number of channels we recorded. Each of the three neurons of
500 the hidden layer exhibit a hyperbolic tangent activation function. The output layer is the decoded
501 output and consists of only one parameter (DoF). Hence, the full decoder incorporates as many MLP
502 networks as desired degrees of freedom. The decoded joints in Experiment 1 were wrist
503 pronation/supination, index and middle finger flexion/extension and ring and little fingers
504 flexion/extension (three DoFs total). The decoded joints in Experiments 2 and 3 were metacarpal-
505 phalangeal joint angle and interphalangeal joint angle of each digit, and thumb opposition/reposition
506 (11 DoFs total). For more robustness, we averaged value of the interphalangeal and metacarpal-
507 phalangeal joints per digit and considered them one DoF for all analyses.

508 Model training defines the weights of each node's contribution to the next layer and in an MLP,
509 all nodes of one layer are connected to each of the nodes of the next layer by these weights. Training
510 was accomplished by minimizing a sum-of-squares error function. A training set with input features x_n
511 where n is the number of time lags ($n = 1, \dots, N$) and desired kinematics t_n has the error function:

$$512 \quad E(w) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \| y(x_n, w) - t_n \|^2$$

513 Here, w is the array of weights of the neurons and y are the predicted kinematics using the feature
514 input. We chose to use the Levenberg-Marquardt method for fitting the network weights due to its
515 faster convergence time than the more typical gradient descent methods.

516 In order to fit the MLP weights in Experiment 1, seven movement repetitions were used for the
517 training set, five for the testing set and three for the validation set. We used 10-fold cross-validation
518 in Experiment 1 and 4-fold cross-validation in Experiments 2 and 3, with the training and test sets in
519 order to determine the optimal weights for testing. In Experiment 2, each session began with a 3-
520 minute training phase in order to record a data set of desired movements consisting of three
521 repetitions of each movement, of which 70% of the time was used for training and 30% for validation.

522 We then performed cross-validation in order to choose the optimal weights for online control. The full
523 model-training process lasted a total of less than ten minutes for all of the subjects, with exact duration
524 depending on the number of EMG channels used. Hence, we emphasize the practical implications of
525 such an algorithm for clinical use.

526 We also performed a preliminary offline experiment in which three able-bodied subjects index
527 and middle finger combined flexion/extension, ulnar grasp/release, and wrist pronation/supination in
528 three different arm positions: arm extended, arm flexed, and arm at rest (supported) shown in
529 Supplementary Figure 1. Subjects performed bilateral volitional alternating movements of each DoF
530 while we optically tracked kinematics of the hand and arm contralateral to the one from which we
531 recorded sEMGs. The MLP decoder was then trained and we performed offline testing of decoder
532 performance. Decoding accuracy of the testing set for one subject is plotted in Figure 2a. With
533 impressive R2 values of 0.82, 0.79 and 0.80 for the index and middle finger flexion/extension, ring
534 and pinky finger flexion/extension, and wrist pronation/supination respectively, the MLP is able to
535 predict movements with high accuracy for each of the DoFs simultaneously. In particular, the decoder
536 adeptly tracks both the sinusoidal flexions and extensions as well as sustained flexion or extension
537 to the full range of motion of the DoFs.

538 For the final “physical” experiment, the architecture of the MLP was changed slightly from the
539 first two experiments. The MLP was designed using TensorFlow’s³⁵ premade DNN regressor class
540 and consisted of three fully connected layers as the other experiments but in this case the hidden
541 layer consisted of thirty neurons that exhibited a ReLU activation function ($\max[0, x]$). The output layer
542 is also the decoded output and consists of only one parameter (DoF). Therefore, there was again one
543 MLP per decoded joint. In this case, joint angle values were kept independent. The loss function was
544 the mean squared error as before. The network was trained using adaptive moment estimation
545 (Adam). During training of experiment 3, subjects were required to perform five repetitions of each
546 movement; four were used as the training set and one for validation. No cross-validation was needed
547 since we could directly see the performance in real time with the robot (~test set). The full model-
548 training process lasted approximately ten minutes for each of the three subjects.

549

550 **Online Control.**

551 Real time software for the MLP was programmed in C++ (Visual Studio 2015)) for experiment 1 and
552 2, which integrated input from the EMG recording systems and sent decoded joint angles to the
553 Modular Prosthetic Limb and to the Allegro Hand simulator in Gazebo. For experiment 3 the real-time
554 software was programmed in Python 3.6, which received the EMG signals and sent decoded joints to
555 the real Allegro Hand. In the C++ software, matrix functions were implemented using the Armadillo
556 class³⁸ and Scilab (Scilab Enterprises 2012). After fitting of the MLP, we extracted features from EMG
557 signals in real time. Here, we use only the most recent 100ms (or 300ms in the third experiment) of
558 EMG data for feature computation. We first normalize EMG amplitudes with means and standard
559 deviations derived from the training data of the same channels and then made prediction updates at
560 33Hz (every 30ms). To obtain a smoother signal, we low-pass filtered the MLP output with a 10-frame
561 moving average and in the third experiment, a Kalman filter was added after the moving average filter.

562

563 **Shared Controller.** The autonomous controller for the shared-control condition adapted from the
564 compliant contact approach published by Sommer and Billard for the maximization of “desired contact
565 points” with objects²³. As soon as the hand is in contact with the object, the controller moves the
566 fingers in directions that increase the area in contact. It stops once it has established a contact at all
567 desired contact points. The digits are controlled in torque-mode at all times. The controller’s principle
568 is based on operational space control. That is, it projects the forces/torques in the nullspace of the
569 contact forces. The controller can also modulate the torques in the fingers’ joints to generate the

570 desired forces at the contact point so as to stabilize the object. For a complete mathematical
571 description of the approach, the reader can refer to Sommer and Billard²³.

572 Depending on the task, different types of contact points and numbers of contacts can be
573 defined. In our implementation, we used a Gazebo simulator of the Allegro Hand, which is a 4-digit
574 robotic hand with simulated contact sensors on the inner, side and top surface of each digit. The hand
575 has three phalanges per digit and joints between the phalanges can all be independently controlled
576 in torque, for a total of 16 actuated degrees of freedom. We defined one desired contact per phalanx
577 of each finger and two for the thumb for a total of 11 desired contacts on the simulator. When the
578 hand is not touching any objects, a proportional-derivative (PD) controller modulates joint torques to
579 achieve the desired joint angle targets. These targets are the angles decoded by the MLP, and
580 streamed to the simulation over UDP. Instead of predefined preshaping as in the previous work,
581 preshaping is left to the user. Indeed, we observed thumb opposition before finger flexion for many
582 subjects (see Supplementary Video 2), which allowed them high grasp stability. In lieu of the drill
583 object tested previously, we presented a thin rectangular bar along with the cylinder and cross joint
584 part (Suppl. Fig. 3a). Each object was tested in one of three random orientations, 30 degrees tilted in
585 either roll, pitch or yaw. This allowed exploration of the full range of object locations with respect to
586 the hand.

587 In the shared control condition, the algorithm attempts to maximize contact area by applying
588 motor torques in the direction of desired contact points. Once a digit comes in contact with an object
589 at any location, the controller will exert joint torques on the hand in order to achieve more desired
590 contact points with the object. The direction of these joint torques is computed as a summation of the
591 normal vector of the contact point with the object and the direction of the desired contact towards that
592 point (Figure 4c). If there is no contact between a digit and an object, that digit is still PD-controlled to
593 achieve the MLP output's target angles. As for the contacts already made between the hand and the
594 object, the shared controller exerts a predefined force, but also permits joint torques in magnitude and
595 direction such that contact force between the desired contact and the object does not change, the
596 contact nullspace. Thus, each digit is allowed to slide along the surface of the object to continue
597 seeking contact with the object at "desired contacts" that have not yet been achieved. Meanwhile, the
598 PD controller continues to compute the joint torques required to achieve MLP-dictated joint angles.
599 The shared controller applies the vector components of these joint torques at already-achieved
600 contacts such that the those contact forces do not change. The result is that the user is still able to
601 move the hand over the object as desired without breaking contact. This feature made object
602 manipulation possible.

603 The shared controller is designed to optimize for maximum contact between hand and object.
604 However, if the difference in desired joint angle of the active shared controller becomes too different
605 (defined in our case as 50 degrees total difference amongst all joints of a digit) from the decoded MLP
606 output, the PD controller takes over again using MLP-decoded joint angles as target angles. Thus,
607 any contact that may already exist could freely be broken.

608

609 **Code availability**

610 The MATLAB code used for data analysis and synthesis of results presented in this study are
611 available at <https://github.com/KZzizzle/0713.git>. Data collection code is available from the
612 corresponding author on reasonable request.

613

614 **Data availability**

615 The data that support the findings of this study are available within the paper and its Supplementary
616 Information. All datasets generated for this study are available from the corresponding author upon
617 reasonable request.

618 **Author Contributions**

619 K.Z. and E.F. designed and carried out Experiments 1-2, and performed analysis of data. A.B. and
620 S.M. were responsible for planning and supervising of the work. N.S. provided code and expertise for
621 the shared controller and contributed greatly to experimental setup. V.M. and F. A. developed the
622 decoding algorithm for Experiment 3. V.M., F.A, S.A. performed the system integration. V.M. S.A
623 performed all the trials for Experiment 3. E.D. aided in experimentation, G.G., G.C., and W.R. were
624 clinical liaisons, and F.P. supervised Experiment 1. K.Z., V.M., and S.A. wrote the manuscript and
625 designed figures. N.S., E.F., E.D., A.B., F.A* and S.M. all contributed critical feedback to the
626 manuscript.

627

628 **Acknowledgements**

629 We wish to acknowledge Brock Wester, Francesco Tenore, and the Johns Hopkins University Applied
630 Physics Laboratory (JHU/APL) for providing the Virtual Integration Environment (VIE), which was
631 developed on the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) Revolutionizing
632 Prosthetics program under Contract No. N66001-10-C-4056. We would also like to thank Francesco
633 Iberite for his assistance in conducting experiments and Alexis Devillars for the development of the
634 Unity model of the hand.

635 This project was partly funded by the Swiss National Competence Center for Research (NCCR) in
636 Robotics, by the Bertarelli Foundation, and by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
637 innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No. 750947 (project
638 BIREHAB).

639

640 **References**

- 641 1. Ziegler-Graham, K., MacKenzie, E. J., Ephraim, P. L., Trivison, T. G. & Brookmeyer, R.
642 Estimating the Prevalence of Limb Loss in the United States: 2005 to 2050. *Arch. Phys. Med.*
643 *Rehabil.* **89**, 422–429 (2008).
- 644 2. Watve, S., Dodd, G., MacDonald, R. & Stoppard, E. R. Upper limb prosthetic rehabilitation.
645 *Orthop. Trauma* **25**, 135–142 (2011).
- 646 3. Geethanjali, P. Myoelectric control of prosthetic hands: state-of-the-art review. *Med. Devices*
647 *Auckl. NZ* **9**, 247 (2016).
- 648 4. Biddiss, E. & Chau, T. Upper-Limb Prosthetics: Critical Factors in Device Abandonment. *Am. J.*
649 *Phys. Med. Rehabil.* **86**, (2007).
- 650 5. Biddiss, E. A. & Chau, T. T. Upper limb prosthesis use and abandonment: A survey of the last
651 25 years. *Prosthet. Orthot. Int.* **31**, 236–257 (2007).
- 652 6. Farina, D. *et al.* The Extraction of Neural Information from the Surface EMG for the Control of
653 Upper-Limb Prostheses: Emerging Avenues and Challenges. *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil.*
654 *Eng.* **22**, 797–809 (2014).
- 655 7. Hioki, M. & Kawasaki, H. Estimation of Finger Joint Angles from sEMG Using a Neural
656 Network Including Time Delay Factor and Recurrent Structure. **2012**, (2012).
- 657 8. Malešević, N. *et al.* Decoding of individual finger movements from surface EMG signals using
658 vector autoregressive hierarchical hidden Markov models (VARHHMM). in *2017 International*
659 *Conference on Rehabilitation Robotics (ICORR)* 1518–1523 (2017).
660 doi:10.1109/ICORR.2017.8009463
- 661 9. Tenore, F. V. G. *et al.* Decoding of Individuated Finger Movements Using Surface
662 Electromyography. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **56**, 1427–1434 (2009).
- 663 10. Smith, R. J., Tenore, F., Huberdeau, D., Etienne-Cummings, R. & Thakor, N. V. Continuous
664 decoding of finger position from surface EMG signals for the control of powered prostheses. in

- 665 *2008 30th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology*
666 *Society* 197–200 (2008). doi:10.1109/IEMBS.2008.4649124
- 667 11. Ngeo, J. G., Tamei, T. & Shibata, T. Continuous and simultaneous estimation of finger
668 kinematics using inputs from an EMG-to-muscle activation model. *J. NeuroEngineering*
669 *Rehabil.* **11**, 122 (2014).
- 670 12. Krasoulis, A., Vijayakumar, S. & Nazarpour, K. Evaluation of regression methods for the
671 continuous decoding of finger movement from surface EMG and accelerometry. in *2015 7th*
672 *International IEEE/EMBS Conference on Neural Engineering (NER)* 631–634 (2015).
673 doi:10.1109/NER.2015.7146702
- 674 13. Cipriani, C. *et al.* Online myoelectric control of a dexterous hand prosthesis by transradial
675 amputees. *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* **19**, 260–270 (2011).
- 676 14. Jiang, N., Dosen, S., Muller, K. R. & Farina, D. Myoelectric Control of Artificial Limbs—Is
677 There a Need to Change Focus? [In the Spotlight]. *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* **29**, 152–150
678 (2012).
- 679 15. Kim, H. K. *et al.* Continuous shared control for stabilizing reaching and grasping with brain-
680 machine interfaces. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **53**, 1164–1173 (2006).
- 681 16. Iturrate, I., Montesano, L. & Minguez, J. Shared-control brain-computer interface for a two
682 dimensional reaching task using EEG error-related potentials. in *2013 35th Annual International*
683 *Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)* 5258–5262
684 (2013). doi:10.1109/EMBC.2013.6610735
- 685 17. Chen, X. *et al.* A shared control policy for center-out movement decoding in motor Brain-
686 machine Interface. *3rd IFAC Conf. Intell. Control Autom. Sci. ICONS 2013* **46**, 345–348 (2013).
- 687 18. Ciancio, A. L. *et al.* Control of Prosthetic Hands via the Peripheral Nervous System. *Front.*
688 *Neurosci.* **10**, 116 (2016).

- 689 19. Došen, S. *et al.* Cognitive vision system for control of dexterous prosthetic hands: Experimental
690 evaluation. *J. NeuroEngineering Rehabil.* **7**, 42–42 (2010).
- 691 20. Light, C. M., Chappell, P. H., Hudgins, B. & Engelhart, K. Intelligent multifunction myoelectric
692 control of hand prostheses. *J. Med. Eng. Technol.* **26**, 139–146 (2002).
- 693 21. Tura, A., Lamberti, C., Davalli, A. & Sacchetti, R. Experimental development of a sensory
694 control system for an upper limb myoelectric prosthesis with cosmetic covering. *J. Rehabil. Res.*
695 *Dev.* **35**, 14–26 (1998).
- 696 22. Fani, S. *et al.* Assessment of Myoelectric Controller Performance and Kinematic Behavior of a
697 Novel Soft Synergy-Inspired Robotic Hand for Prosthetic Applications. *Front. Neurorobotics* **10**,
698 11 (2016).
- 699 23. Sommer, N. & Billard, A. Multi-contact haptic exploration and grasping with tactile sensors.
700 *Robot. Auton. Syst.* **85**, 48–61 (2016).
- 701 24. Celadon, N., Došen, S., Binder, I., Ariano, P. & Farina, D. Proportional estimation of finger
702 movements from high-density surface electromyography. *J. NeuroEngineering Rehabil.* **13**, 73
703 (2016).
- 704 25. Segil, J. L., Controzzi, M., Weir, R. F. ff & Cipriani, C. Comparative study of state-of-the-art
705 myoelectric controllers for multigrasp prosthetic hands. *J. Rehabil. Res. Dev.* **51**, 1439–1454
706 (2014).
- 707 26. Mathiowetz, V., Volland, G., Kashman, N. & Weber, K. Adult norms for the Box and Block Test
708 of manual dexterity. *Am. J. Occup. Ther.* **39**, 386–391 (1985).
- 709 27. Park, E. & Meek, S. G. Fatigue compensation of the electromyographic signal for prosthetic
710 control and force estimation. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **40**, 1019–1023 (1993).
- 711 28. Tkach, D., Huang, H. & Kuiken, T. A. Study of stability of time-domain features for
712 electromyographic pattern recognition. *J. NeuroEngineering Rehabil.* **7**, 21 (2010).

- 713 29. Asghari Oskoei, M. & Hu, H. Myoelectric control systems—A survey. *Biomed. Signal Process.*
714 *Control* **2**, 275–294 (2007).
- 715 30. Micera, S., Carpaneto, J. & Raspopovic, S. Control of Hand Prostheses Using Peripheral
716 Information. *IEEE Rev. Biomed. Eng.* **3**, 48–68 (2010).
- 717 31. Wan, B. *et al.* Study on fatigue feature from forearm SEMG signal based on wavelet analysis. in
718 *2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics* 1229–1232 (2010).
719 doi:10.1109/ROBIO.2010.5723504
- 720 32. Zardoshti-Kermani, M., Wheeler, B. C., Badie, K. & Hashemi, R. M. EMG feature evaluation
721 for movement control of upper extremity prostheses. *IEEE Trans. Rehabil. Eng.* **3**, 324–333
722 (1995).
- 723 33. Phinyomark, A., Phukpattaranont, P. & Limsakul, C. Feature reduction and selection for EMG
724 signal classification. *Expert Syst. Appl.* **39**, 7420–7431 (2012).
- 725 34. Chu, J. U., Moon, I. & Mun, M. S. A Real-Time EMG Pattern Recognition System Based on
726 Linear-Nonlinear Feature Projection for a Multifunction Myoelectric Hand. *IEEE Trans.*
727 *Biomed. Eng.* **53**, 2232–2239 (2006).
- 728 35. Abadi, M. *et al.* Tensorflow: A system for large-scale machine learning. in 265–283 (2016).
729